

ACCURATE PREDICTION OF THERMAL DEFORMATION OF SANDWICH PANELS CONSIDERING THE EFFECT OF ADHESIVE

Shigenori Kabashima

*Advanced Technology R&D Center, Mitsubishi Electric Corporation
Miyashimo1-1-57, Sagamihara, Kanagawa, 229 Japan*

SUMMARY: Adhesive has been reported to influence the thermo-mechanical behavior of honeycomb sandwich panels with very thin skins which are widely used for satellite structures. Though high dimensional stability is a great interest in the aerospace field, the effect of adhesive has never been quantitatively investigated. This paper describes the effect of adhesive and the computational modeling of sandwich panels.

First, dimensionally stable sandwich panels with different bonds were fabricated and their coefficients of thermal expansion(CTEs) were evaluated. For this measurement, a high precision measuring system was developed. Second, a finite element model was built by simulating a unit cell of a honeycomb sandwich panel. In this model, the effect of adhesive was taken in to account. Suitable boundary conditions were discussed here, so that repetitive structures of a sandwich panel could be effectively analyzed by the unit cell model. Finally, the calculated CTEs were compared with the experimental result and the thermo-mechanical behavior of sandwich panels was discussed.

KEYWORDS: honeycomb sandwich panel, coefficient of thermal expansion, adhesive, finite element method

INTRODUCTION

Honeycomb sandwich panels with thin PMC(Polymer Matrix Composite) skins have been used to fabricate dimensionally stable satellite structures[1][2]. In the severest cases, CTEs of honeycomb sandwich panels are required to be controlled with the accuracy of 0.1 ppm/K. Recently developed pitch based high modulus graphite fibers have good potentiality to realize this kind of structures. However, this is not a easy task because a methodology to accurately predict thermal deformation of sandwich panels is not established. In actual design of satellite structures, thermo-mechanical behavior of sandwich panels is often calculated by laminate theory assuming that honeycomb core and adhesive are plies of homogeneous materials[3]. However this method does not always produce good results because of complex behavior of constitutional materials; honeycomb core and adhesive. Equivalent properties of honeycomb cores are reported to have dependency on the properties of skin materials[4]. Besides, orthotropic behavior of honeycomb cores are well known. Form of adhesive is also known to impact the thermo-mechanical property of sandwich panels, although this effect have never been quantitatively studied. Finite element method(FEM) is thought to be helpful to study the

thermal deformation of sandwich panels considering the effects of all the constitutional materials[5]. In the present paper, a FEM model schematizing the detailed structure of honeycomb sandwich panels is presented, in which the effect of honeycomb core and adhesive on the thermal deformation is taken into account. In order to make the simulation effective, the models are focused on the structure of a unit cell of honeycomb sandwich panels. Validation of these models is also discussed comparing with experimental tests.

EXPERIMENTAL TEST

In order to evaluate the influence of adhesive, dimensionally stable sandwich panels with different skin/core bonds were fabricated and their CTEs were measured. For this purpose, a high precision CTE measuring system was originally developed.

Test Specimens

Three kinds of sandwich panels were manufactured with materials shown in Table 1; thin PMC skin (high-modulus graphite fiber reinforced epoxy), aluminum honeycomb core and light weight film adhesive. K13A/934 woven fabric prepreg whose thickness is 0.07mm/ply was autoclave cured with (0/90)/(+45) configuration making the stacking sequence of sandwich panel symmetric as a whole. This is a typical configuration of sandwich panels for antenna reflectors. Then the skins and cores were bonded. Table 2 shows the skin/core bonding conditions. The amount of adhesive was controlled by the number of film sheets stacked. The two kinds of adhesive forms are shown in Figure 1. Film adhesive was heated in an oven after placed on honeycomb cores for reticulation.

Table 1 Materials for sandwich panel

part	material
skin	K13A/934 (pitch based graphite fiber/epoxy)
core	Hexcel aluminum honeycomb 3/8in/ 5056/ 0.0007in/9.35mm
adhesive	FM-96U (film adhesive, 0.015psf/ply)

Table 2 Skin/core bonding condition

specimen	adhesive	
	quantity	form
Panel#1	0.015psf	reticulated
Panel#2	0.015psf	as placed
Panel#3	0.030psf	reticulated

Figure 1 Forms of adhesive

CTE Measurement System

In order to evaluate the thermal deformation of sandwich panels, a high precision CTE measurement system was developed. The system consists of a temperature controlled chamber and an electro-optical displacement detecting system (Figure 2). The chamber is equipped with a pipe-shaped heater and a liquid nitrogen supplier. The maximum size of specimens for this chamber is 300*500*100mm. The temperature in the chamber is controlled between -150 and +150°C with the variation of $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ by circulating nitrogen gas. This temperature range meets the requirements of satellite structures. OPT-FOLLOW7100C (YAMAN LTD.) is utilized for displacement detecting system which consists of two electro-optical cameras and amplifiers. The cameras detect optical targets colored with black and white through optical fibers attached with magnification lenses. The deformation of a specimen due to temperature change is measured from the differential displacement of two targets mounted on the specimen. Targets need to be lightened with stable and intense light. Xenon lamps were chosen for the light source so that the specimen would not be heated during the measurement. Relative position of the two magnification lenses and specimen need to be unchanged during the testing. In particular, stability of the distance between the two lenses directly affects the performance of the system. Therefore, zero-expansive glass was used to fix the lenses (Figure 3).

Calibration of the displacement detecting system was carried out by measuring the displacement of a target attached to a micrometer. Then the measuring accuracy of the whole system was examined using zero-expansive glass and low expansive laminate composites as specimens with known CTEs. As the result, this system was found to have accuracy of 0.1 ppm/K and reproducibility of 0.05 ppm/K.

Test Procedure

The CTEs of the specimens between 0 and 50°C were measured. The specimens were dried in a vacuum oven under 80°C for 24 hours prior to testing and placed in the chamber after mounted with optical targets colored with black and white (Figure 4). Specimens were cooled at 0°C for 60 minutes, then heated to 50°C at the rate of 2°C/min and kept for 60 minutes. The average values of CTE between 0 and 50°C were obtained from the measured displacement of

targets caused by the deformation of specimen due to the temperature change. The measurement was carried out both for L-direction and W-direction (Figure 1).

Figure 2 Configuration of CTE measurement system for honeycomb sandwich panels

Figure 3 Configuration of magnification

Figure 4 Test specimen with optical targets

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

In order to study the thermo-mechanical behavior of sandwich panels and develop an effective method to predict the deformation, a FEM model simulating a unit cell of sandwich structure was built.

Unit cell Model

A FEM model simulating the thermo-mechanical behavior of honeycomb sandwich panel was built with the following assumptions;

1. The sandwich panel is plane and large enough compared with the unit cell.
2. The ply configuration of the sandwich panel is symmetrical.
3. The sandwich panel has no temperature variation.

Figure 5 shows the generated model. I-DEAS was utilized as the FEM analysis program. Thin shell element was chosen both for the honeycomb core and the skin because no bending effect was expected in the structure. Effect of adhesive was not considered here. All necessary properties of the skin were experimentally measured. As for the stiffness of honeycomb cell wall, elastic modulus of aluminum is not applicable because core reaction capability is considered to be reduced due to deformed condition of the thin cell wall. Therefore stiffness of the cell wall was calculated from the equivalent compressive modulus of the honeycomb core which was measured by the material supplier, which indicates the reducing proportion from aluminum stiffness. The CTE of the honeycomb cell wall was considered to be equal to that of aluminum.

In general, honeycomb sandwich panels cannot be correctly simulated by a unit cell model because of their repetitive structures. Though models simulating large number of cells are expected to produce good results, that kind of models require a lot of time to be built and calculated. In order to make the simulation effective, a refined unit cell model is desirable. When we considered the assumptions of this problem, it was surmised that every unit cell is symmetrical with its neighboring cells because all the cells are identical in their structure and

condition. Hence this symmetrical condition was introduced as a boundary condition for the unit cell model. When we compared the thermal deformation calculated from this unit cell model with that from a multi-cell model that contains 400 cells, they were found to agree well. Thus this unit cell model was considered to be valid to calculate the CTEs of sandwich panels.

Modeling of Skin/core Adhesive

Next, skin/core adhesive was schematized considering its form. Thin shell element and bar element were used for the as placed and the reticulated adhesive respectively(Figure 6). Thin shell elements schematizing the as placed adhesive were placed to overlap with skin elements. Bar elements schematizing the reticulated adhesive were placed between nodes on the edges of honeycomb cell. The CTE and elastic modulus of the adhesive were measured using a thermo-mechanical analyzer (Shinku-Riko DL-7000Y-RH) and dynamic mechanical analyzer (TA Instruments DMA983), respectively. CTEs of Panel#1, #2, #3 were calculated by giving these models the temperature change of 1°C.

Figure 5 Unit cell model of honeycomb sandwich panel

Figure 6 FEM models in which adhesive is schematized

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 4 shows the measured and calculated CTEs of the specimens. The measurement shows that reticulation and reduction of adhesive makes CTEs of sandwich panels lower. Further, this effect of adhesive is correctly calculated. Focusing on the orthotropy of the panels, it was a little underestimated by the simulation; the calculated differences of CTEs between L-direction and W-direction are smaller than measured values. The walls oriented to the L-direction are made of two plies of aluminum foils bonded together and their thickness is doubled. Therefore apparent elastic modulus of these walls is larger than that of other walls. This variation of stiffness of the honeycomb walls is considered to emphasize the orthotropic behavior of the sandwich panel. In total, the prediction and the measurement agreed very well.

Table 3: Measured and calculated CTEs of the specimens

specimen	measured CTE(ppm/K)		calculated CTE(ppm/K)	
	L-direction	W-direction	L-direction	W-direction
Panel #1 (0.015psf, reticulated)	-0.52	-0.66	-0.57	-0.62
Panel #2 (0.015psf, as placed)	-0.29	-0.37	-0.26	-0.30
Panel #3 (0.030psf, reticulated)	-0.25	-0.36	-0.40	-0.44

CONCLUSIONS

By studying the effect of adhesive on the thermo-mechanical behavior of sandwich panels and a FEM model simulating a unit cell of the structure, the following was concluded.

1. Three kinds of sandwich panels with different bonds were fabricated and their CTEs were evaluated. This measurement showed that reticulation and reduction of adhesive make CTEs of sandwich panels lower.
2. In order to evaluate CTEs of sandwich panels, a accurate CTE measuring system was originally developed. This system was proved to have the measuring accuracy of 0.1ppm/K.
3. A FEM model simulating a unit cell of sandwich panels was built considering the effect of adhesive. The CTEs calculated from this model agreed very well with the measured values.

The developed predicting method is very helpful in designing satellite structures.

REFERENCES

1. Kelly J. Dodson et. al., "Thermal stability considerations for space flight optical benches", 34th International SAMPE symposium, pp.1578-1689 (1989).
2. F.Grimalde et. al., "Development of dimensionally stable lightweight composite satellite antenna structures", 34th International SAMPE symposium, pp.1590-1602 (1989).
3. L. Scolamiero, "Modeling of honeycomb for sandwich CTE prediction", ESA SP-321, pp.427-430 (1991).
4. H. Groth, "Thermal stability of sandwich reflectors", *ESA SP-243, pp.133-139 (1986)*.
5. C. C. Chemis et.al., "Composite sandwich thermostructural behavior: computational simulation", NASA 0948, pp.370-381(1986).